

Toxicological Impact of Pesticides in Mammals and the Antioxidant Mitigation by Natural Ascorbic Acid

Maham Saleem^{1*}, Kashif Ali¹, Muhammad Farhan Nasir¹, Sadaqat Ali², Mehak Mughal¹, Hibba Rasheed¹, Ayesha Abeer¹, Muhammad Farrukh Mushtaq¹, Alia Hussain³, Afreen Fatima¹, Saima Liaqat¹ and Kiran Javed¹

1. Department of Zoology, Division of Science and Technology, University of Education Lahore, Punjab Pakistan
2. Institute of Zoology, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, 60800, Pakistan
3. Institute of Molecular Biology & Biotechnology, University of Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

*Corresponding author e-mail: mahamsaleem7855@gmail.com

SUMMARY

The study was aimed to evaluate the protective effects of lemon extract against the pesticide imidacloprid. Adult rabbits of either sex weighing 1 kg were selected and housed in cages in a room where the temperature was maintained at $27^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The animals were allowed to acclimatize to the surroundings for 5 days. Then, the rabbits were divided into six groups. The weight of each individual animal was calculated before the administration of imidacloprid (IMI). The standard IMI (1 ml/kg) was administered to the rabbits to induce toxicity in the lungs, lipid profile, and hormones. After 24 hours the blood was taken through the ear vein to confirm the induction of lipid and endocrine toxicity. The rabbits were then divided into six groups with 5 rabbits in each group. The groups were named A (Control), B (IMI control), and experimental groups (C, D, E, and F). Test extracts of *vitamin C* and silymarin were administered orally with distilled water four times at 12-hour intervals for a period of 72 hours to the experimental groups, while the control groups (A and B) received a normal diet. Group C was treated with vitamin C, extracts at an oral dose of 0.2 ml/kg. Group D was treated with vitamin C extracts at an oral dose of 0.4 ml/kg, and Group E was treated with vitamin C extracts at a dose of 0.6 ml/kg. Group F was treated with silymarin, at an oral dose of 1 ml/kg. The effect of imidacloprid pesticide can be reduced by using vitamin C (lemon extract) on the lipid profile and hormones of rabbits, as seen in previous results. Moreover, syrup silymarin is also very effective reducing toxicity.

Keywords: Pesticide, vitamin, Imidacloprid

INTRODUCTION

The pesticides category of chemicals encompasses nematicides, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, rodenticides, and molluscicides (Bernardes et al., 2015). It is well acknowledged that pesticides are crucial to agricultural development since they lower agricultural product losses and increase food affordability, output, and quality (Tudi et al., 2021; Strassemeyer et al., 2017). There was an upsurge in the creation of pesticides during World War II to improve food supply and control insect-transported diseases (1939-1945). In addition, the increase in food production during this time was attributed to the extensive use of synthetic crop protection agents beginning in the 1940s (Bernardes et al., 2015). In addition, global pesticide production rose from 0.2 million tons in the 1950s to nearly 5 million tons in 2000, at an approximate 11% annual pace (Carvalho et al., 2017). Approximately 3 billion kilograms of pesticides

are applied globally every year (Hayes et al., 2017). Pesticides are applied to 3 billion kilograms (3 billion tons) of crops worldwide every year, however, only 1% of it is accurately targeted towards insect pests, Bernardes et al 2015. There is rampant use and misuse of pesticides. These pesticides then find their way into the environment. Residual pesticides, particularly insecticides, are not fully utilized on the intended plants but instead infiltrate non-target plants and environmental surroundings. As a result, pesticide pollution has contaminated the ecosystem and had detrimental effects.

When pesticides come into contact with untreated tissues, they are absorbed by plants or animals. Systemic herbicides penetrate the plant and can reach untreated sections of the leaves, stems, or roots. Even when the pesticide is only partially sprayed, it is still effective at killing weeds. They kill target pests by efficiently penetrating plant tissues and moving through the plant vascular system (Abubakar et al., 2020). Imidacloprid, a neonicotinoid pesticide, is utilized globally because of its targeted toxicity toward insects. The residues can enter the food chain, making it essential to examine the possible harmful impacts of exposure to imidacloprid. This review outlines existing information regarding the reproductive toxicity and endocrine-disrupting effects of imidacloprid in lab animals. Studies primarily involving laboratory rats have indicated negative impacts of imidacloprid on reproductive capacity in both parent and offspring generations, along with effects on offspring development. Similar to various pesticides, imidacloprid might also function as an endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC). It might disturb metabolic balance, lead to obesity, and interfere with steroid production by inhibiting the activities of cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes. The negative impacts of imidacloprid could present significant hazards for reproduction and development, leading to lasting effects in later life. Neonicotinoid insecticides, the leading category of synthetic neuroactive insecticides, are extensively utilized to protect crops and livestock from a variety of pests (Mikolić et al., 2018).

Imidacloprid (IMI) [1-(6-chloro-3-pyridylmethyl)-N-nitroimidazolidin-2-ylideneamine] is a chlorinated analogue of nicotine and the first neonicotinoid registered for use as a pesticide by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA). Since its introduction in 1992, imidacloprid's usage has grown annually due to its selective toxicity and apparent safety for humans, accounting for 41.5% of neonicotinoid usage (Mikolić et al., 2018). It is classified as a "Group E" carcinogen, indicating no evidence of carcinogenicity in humans (Mikolić et al., 2018). Neonicotinoid insecticides act as agonists of insect nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs), which are crucial for synaptic transmission in the central nervous system (Mikolić et al., 2018). Due to structural differences between mammalian and insect nAChRs and a higher binding affinity for insect nAChRs, imidacloprid is considered a selective toxicant (Mikolić et al., 2018). Its oral LD50 in rats and mice is 450 and 131 mg/kg of body weight, respectively (Mikolić et al., 2018). While imidacloprid is mildly toxic to mammals, it can impact the heart, kidneys, and other organs, causing gastrointestinal irritation, neurological symptoms, or even death. Reports have indicated adverse effects in mammals, including teratogenic (Mikolić et al., 2018), mutagenic (Bagri et al., 2016), neurotoxic (Mikolić et al., 2018), and immunotoxic effects (Mikolić et al., 2018).

The toxicity of imidacloprid is dose-dependent, as reported by a study that evaluated the effects of 30 days of oral administration of 1/85 LD50 and 1/120 LD50 of imidacloprid on thyroid toxicity in female rats (Mikolić et al., 2018). and a study of hematological and biochemical parameters in male rats after oral administration of 0.125 LD50 and 0.1 LD50 of imidacloprid, which correspond to the levels found in and on treated cucumbers one hour and one day after the application of imidacloprid, respectively (Mikolić et al., 2018). In this mini-review, however, we focus on the current knowledge of the adverse effects of imidacloprid on reproductive and endocrine function as evidenced by recent animal studies.

Imidacloprid is one of the most commonly used insecticides in the world (Van Dijk et al., 2013). It used to prevent sucking insects on crops and seeds (Naiel et al., 2020). Despite its benefits, such as safety for the pesticide operator, unique structure, and selectivity, a report by the European Food Safety Authority involved a hazard assessment of imidacloprid for bees (Rortais et al., 2017). The use of three neonicotinoid pesticides, including imidacloprid, had been restricted by the European Commission from 2013 to 2015 (Baroso, 2013). Additionally, the European Commission restrictions do not allow imidacloprid usage in glasshouses and all-field applications after flowering, as there could be probable releases to shallow water from these suppliers, or from veterinary and biocidal applications (Smit et al., 2015). Imidacloprid is a water-soluble pesticide, persistent in soil and, under field conditions, usually non-volatile, and incredibly persistent in soil, aquatic sediments, and water (Tomizawa, 2013). Consequently, imidacloprid can also induce toxicity in aquatic invertebrates and juvenile fish at under low levels and is considered to be acutely toxic to birds (Naiel et al., 2020).

Recently, a growing number of studies have been conducted on the aquatic ecotoxicity of imidacloprid. Thus, the toxic doses of imidacloprid for aquatic invertebrates must be determined. There is also a lack of information regarding the environmental fate of imidacloprid in aquatic life, such as biodegradation and bioaccumulation. The toxicity of commercial preparations may also be influenced by potential interactions between the pesticide and the solvent (Naiel et al., 2020). While pesticides are formulated through very strict regulatory processes to work with reasonable certainty and minimal impact on human health and the environment, commercial additives or organophosphates can synergize or antagonize the toxicity of the ingredient (Naiel et al., 2020). Many studies have shown that the additive compounds in commercial pesticide formulations can cause toxicity and induce cellular damage directly from the active ingredient (Naiel et al., 2020). Despite their lower capacity for bioconcentration, the increasing release of these compounds into aquatic environments may be acutely toxic and cause chronic sublethal disorders. In addition, fish will not have toxins in their tissues in the natural ecosystem that are higher than those in the environments in which they survive. Using commercial formulations, moreover, can increase the accumulation rate compared with the active ingredient (Iturburu et al., 2017).

Insecticides are well-known pesticides that disrupt the nervous system and damage the exoskeletons of pests, effectively eliminating or deterring them (NPIC). Since the introduction of various synthetic insecticides—such as organophosphates (Amjad et al., 2018), carbamates (1970s), pyrethroids (1980s), and neonicotinoids

(late 1980s)—agricultural output has increased due to their effectiveness in pest control (Amjad et al., 2018). Insecticides can act as neurotoxins (e.g., imidacloprid and lambda-cyhalothrin), respiration inhibitors (e.g., organotins and propargite), growth inhibitors and regulators (e.g., hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen), and stomach poisons (e.g., deltamethrin). Their effectiveness is typically measured by dosage metrics, including median effective concentration (LC50), also known as median lethal concentration (LC50), and lethal median dose (LD50), which account for the different species of arthropods (Amjad et al., 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Vehari is the 62nd largest city in Pakistan, located approximately 100 km (62 mi) from the historic city of Multan. It lies along the Multan-Delhi Road, which was constructed by Emperor Sher Shah Suri. At an altitude of 135 m (443 ft), Vehari has a population of around 330,000 and covers an area of approximately 4,373 square kilometers. The city's coordinates are approximately 30.0444° N latitude and 72.3554° E longitude. The average elevation of the district is about 142 meters (466 feet) above sea level, with slight variations in altitude throughout the area.

Figure 1: The structural formula of Imidacloprid.

EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL

Rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*)

Adult rabbits were selected and weighed ranged of 1kg \pm 200g were housed in a cage with a temperature of 27°C \pm 1°C. For four days, the rabbits were given a regular meal with the proper acclimatization of the environment.

Natural Treatment

Lemon juice is rich in vitamin C and contain smaller amounts of B vitamins, such as thiamin, riboflavin, and niacin. It can comprise up to 5% or more of its weight in citric acid. In a study, lemon was used as an antioxidant to mitigate the effects of IMI toxicity in rabbits. Silymarin was utilized as the standard drug to evaluate hepatoprotective activity, with a sample obtained from the market. The silymarin suspension was prepared at a concentration of 1mg/ml.

The standard *IMI* dose of 1 ml/kg was administered to the rabbits based on their weight to induce toxicity affecting the lungs, lipid profile, and hormone levels. After 24 hours, blood samples were collected from the ear vein to confirm the induction of lipid and endocrine toxicity. The rabbits were divided into six groups, each containing with five rabbits. The groups were designated as A (Control), B (*IMI* control) and four experimental groups (C, D, E and F).

The experimental groups received oral doses of *Vitamin C* and silymarin mixed with distilled water, administered four times at 12-hour intervals over a 72-hour period. The control groups (A and B) received a normal diet. Group C was treated with *Vitamin C* extracts at an oral dose of 0.2 ml/kg, Group D received 0.4 ml/kg, Group E was given 0.6 ml/kg, and Group F was administered silymarin, at dose of 1 ml/kg.

Fixed organs underwent repeated washes in 70% ethanol for dehydration, followed by treatment with xylene for clarity. Tissues were then infiltrated with molten wax and embedded in wax blocks using steel molds set in plastic blocks. First, molten wax was poured into the bottom of the mold, after which the fetus was positioned with the head facing upward, and we allowed it to solidify. Serial sections measuring 4.5 to 5.5 μm were cut using a microtome. These sections were stained with Ehrlich's Hematoxylin and mounted with Canada balsam. Xylene-dipped cover slips were placed over each section on the slide, and the sections were examined under a microscope at magnifications of 40x and 100x for histological studies (Corrin B., 1981).

Hormonal & Haematological Analysis

Different hormonal levels were measured using the analytical techniques of (Mirghaed et al. (2017)). The studied hormones include luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), thyroxine (T4), triiodothyronine (T3), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and testosterone from the serum of rabbits.

Following the administration of microplastics and treatments with ameliorants, blood treated with EDTA will be utilized to assess hematological parameters, including erythrocyte count (red blood cell [RBC]), hemoglobin, hematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), platelet (PLT) count, total leucocyte count (white blood cell [WBC]), and differential count (five parameters: neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes), as measured by a completely automated hematology analyzer (Mirghaed et al., 2017).

The serum collected after centrifugation was analyzed for biochemical parameters, including creatinine, albumin, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), amylase, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), calcium, total cholesterol, glucose, HDL cholesterol, iron, phosphorus, total protein, triglycerides, urea, and zinc, using the Humastar 300 biochemistry analyzer (Human GmbH, Germany) (Bharti et al., 2021).

RESULTS

Group A, being the control group of experiment, shows no significant changes, while group B, the *IMI* intoxicated group, had significant changes. These changes reduce in

groups C,D,E, and F when treated with different concentrations of vitamin C. Detailed results of the experimental groups are shared below in tables.

Table 1: Haematological and serum biochemical analysis of all treatment groups of rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) after intoxicated with imiloprid and Vitamin C.

Parameters	GroupA	GroupB	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
RBC	9.4±0.526	4.0±0.16	6.1±0.523	6.3±0.53	8.4±0.48	8.3±0.68
WBC	13.1±0.68	14.07±0.72	11.5±0.64	10.9±0.13	12.1±0.64	12.1±0.19
PLT	313±1.4	240±0.67	291±0.73	290±0.65	310±0.84	305±0.28
Hb	14.07± 0.14	14.07±0.61	14.07±0.36	14.07±0.50	14.07±0.60	14.07±0.31
PCV	48.54± 0.62	48.54±0.57	48.54±0.47	48.54±0.66	48.54±0.67	48.54±0.62
MCV	46.22±0.47	46.22±0.95	46.22±0.69	46.22±0.72	46.22±0.97	46.22±0.74
MCH	15.07±0.08	15.07±0.61	15.07±0.55	15.07±0.51	15.07±0.64	15.07±0.27
MCHC	33.07±0.38	33.07±0.51	33.07±0.48	33.07±0.60	33.07±0.84	33.07±0.39
Glucose	81.49±0.48	81.49±0.69	81.49±1.0	81.49±0.53	81.49±0.63	81.49±0.15
T. Protein	70.26±0.54	70.26±0.73	70.26±0.31	70.26±0.18	70.26±0.41	70.26±0.49
Urea	14.68±0.46	14.68±0.25	14.68±0.73	14.68±0.26	14.68±0.48	14.68±0.39
Creatinine	.75±0.01	.75±0.11	.75±0.01	.75±0.01	.75±0.01	.75±0.01
T. Bilirubin	1.10±0.01	1.10±0.01	1.10±0.01	1.10±0.04	1.10±0.01	1.10±0.04
AST	80.82±0.57	80.82±0.64	80.82±0.26	80.82±0.56	80.82±0.44	80.82±0.31
ALT	42.60±0.39	42.60±0.40	42.60±0.18	42.60±0.53	42.60±0.48	42.60±0.12
ALP	38.86±0.57	38.86±0.39	38.86±0.56	38.86±0.34	38.86±0.60	38.86±0.52

Table 2: Lipid Profile Analysis in rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniulus*) after intoxicated with after intoxicated with imiloprid and Vitamin C

Parameters	GroupA	GroupB	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
CH	170.32±0.55	170.32±0.56	170.32±0.45	170.32±1.8	170.32±0.74	170.32±0.5
TGL	105.40±1.14	105.40±1.14	105.40±1.14	105.40±1.4	105.40±0.83	105.40±1.4
LDL	120.26±0.66	120.26±1.14	120.26±1.14	120.26±1.4	120.26±1.30	120.26±1.4
HDL	30.60±0.56	30.60±0.62	30.60±0.52	30.60±0.60	30.60±0.89	30.60±0.28
UA	5.58±0.48	5.58±0.45	5.58±0.42	5.58±0.55	5.58±0.55	5.58±0.44

Table 3: LH, FSH, T4, T3, TSH and Testosterone levels in rabbit treated with after intoxicated with imiloprid and Vitamin C

Parameters	GroupA	GroupB	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
LH(UI/L)	6.03±0.300 ^a	3.32±0.410 ^c	3.79±0.575 ^{bc}	4.26±0.114 ^b	5.70±0.689 ^a	6.18±0.192 ^a
FSH(UI/L)	8.26±0.466 ^b	6.50±0.429 ^d	7.41±0.637 ^c	8.11±0.078 ^b	8.63±0.545 ^{ab}	9.02±0.208 ^a
T4(nmol/L)	125.36±1.34 ^a	92.86±0.862 ^d	98.28±1.209 ^c	97.82±0.673 ^c	117.99±0.937 ^b	125.43±0.993 ^a
T3(ng/dL)	331.04±0.837 ^b	270.59±0.540 ^d	284.82±1.608 ^c	284.93±0.930 ^c	331.27±0.860 ^b	334.26±1.250 ^a
TSH(mIU/L)	0.18±0.148 ^{ab}	0.39±0.397 ^a	0.13±0.011 ^b	0.14±0.011 ^b	0.14±0.011 ^b	0.15±0.011 ^b
Testosterone(ng/ml)	8.46±0.591 ^a	6.10±0.234 ^c	6.18±0.485 ^c	7.02±0.593 ^b	8.99±0.050 ^a	8.94±0.206 ^a

DISCUSSION

It was stated that a significant number of environmental contaminants, such as pesticides, present a growing threat to both humans and animals (Jin et al., 2013, 2014; Defarge et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019). These substances are commonly referred to as EDCs, which are characterized as external agents that disrupt the production, movement, or function of endogenous hormones that regulate homeostasis (Gray et al., 2001; Ahmad et al., 2017). The extensive application of IMI

has heightened the potential risk of residue exposure for humans and non-target animals (Morrison et al., 2018). Multiple earlier studies have associated the toxicity of IMI with hepatotoxic, nephrotoxic, and neurotoxic effects in various experimental models (Arfat et al., 2014; Lonare et al., 2014). Several earlier studies have also clearly shown that IMI might interfere with the endocrine system (Gu et al., 2013; Mohamed et al., 2016; Mzid et al., 2017).

In the current study, six groups were formed in which groups A and B were the control groups of the experiment. They showed standard ranges of hematology and serum analysis, which were RBC 9.4 ± 0.526 , WBC 13.1 ± 0.68 , PLT 313 ± 1.4 , Hb 14.07 ± 0.14 , PCV 48.54 ± 0.62 , MCV 46.22 ± 0.47 , MCH 15.07 ± 0.08 , MCHC 33.07 ± 0.38 , Glucose 81.49 ± 0.48 , T. Protein 70.26 ± 0.54 , Urea 14.68 ± 0.46 , Creatinine 0.75 ± 0.01 , T. Bilirubin 1.10 ± 0.01 , AST 80.82 ± 0.57 , ALT 42.60 ± 0.39 , ALP 38.86 ± 0.57 . The standard values for the lipid profile of groups A and B were CH 170.32 ± 0.55 , TGL 105.40 ± 1.14 , LDL 120.26 ± 0.66 , HDL 30.60 ± 0.56 , UA 5.58 ± 0.48 . The hormone levels of groups A and B were LH (UI/L) 6.03 ± 0.300 , FSH (UI/L) 8.26 ± 0.466 , T4 (nmol/L) 125.36 ± 1.340 , T3 (ng/dL) 331.04 ± 0.837 , TSH (mIU/L) 0.18 ± 0.148 , Testosterone (ng/ml) 8.46 ± 0.591 . Meanwhile, groups C and D were intoxicated with varying doses of imidacloprid, which showed a significant change in these values. RBC, WBC, PLT, Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, MCHC, Glucose, T. Protein, Urea, Creatinine, T. Bilirubin, AST, ALT, and ALP values showed a decrease in groups C and D to 6.1 ± 0.523 , 11.5 ± 0.64 , 291 ± 0.73 , 14.07 ± 0.36 , 48.54 ± 0.47 , 46.22 ± 0.69 , 15.07 ± 0.55 , 33.07 ± 0.48 , 81.49 ± 1.0 , 70.26 ± 0.31 , 14.68 ± 0.73 , 0.75 ± 0.01 , 1.10 ± 0.01 , 80.82 ± 0.26 , 42.60 ± 0.18 , 38.86 ± 0.56 . In groups C and D, the levels of LH (UI/L), FSH (UI/L), T4 (nmol/L), T3 (ng/dL), TSH (mIU/L) and Testosterone (ng/ml) also decreased from the standard values to 3.79 ± 0.575 , 7.41 ± 0.637 , 98.28 ± 1.209 , 284.82 ± 1.608 , 0.13 ± 0.011 , and 6.18 ± 0.485 , respectively.

Tonietto (2022) supports our findings; he worked on male Wistar rats and analyzed that in blood, there was a drop in mean corpuscular hemoglobin as well as mean corpuscular hemoglobin level and a boost in serum butyrylcholinesterase exertion. Thus, subchronic use of an IMI-based pesticide prompted behavioral and systemic disabilities in rats. Razaa (2023) also states that exposure to imidacloprid can impact hematological indicators and result in a reduction in hemoglobin, hematocrit, and red blood cell (RBC) levels.

Whereas Groups E and F were the groups treated with vitamin C after intoxication with imidacloprid. Group E shows a slight increase in hematological values, while Group F shows significant relevance to the control group.

Elgharib (2023) supports our finding; he worked on rats, and his results also showed a significant decrease in albumin and total protein and an increase in globulin, total, and direct bilirubin. Additionally, there was a rise in ALT, AST, and ALP concentrations. Together with the antioxidants GST, GSH, CAT, and SOD, the MDA of the cadmium group increased compared to Group A. However, when vitamin C was added to cadmium chloride, the results showed a discernible improvement in the parameters being studied, suggesting that vitamin C has a therapeutic effect on cadmium chloride toxicity in rats.

CONCLUSION

The effect of the imdacloprid pesticide can be reduced by using vitamin C (lemon extract) on the lipid profile and hormones of rabbits, as seen in previous results. Moreover, silymarin syrup is also very effective in reducing toxicity.

REFERENCES

- Abbassy, M. A., Marzouk, M. A., Nasr, H. M., & Mansy, A. S. M. (2014). Effect of imidacloprid and tetraconazole on various haematological and biochemical parameters in male albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Journal of Political Sciences & Public Affairs*, 2(1), 122.
- Abdulra'uf, L. B., & Tan, G. H. (2013). Multivariate study of parameters in the determination of pesticide residues in apple by headspace solid phase microextraction coupled to gas chromatography–mass spectrometry using experimental factorial design. *Food Chemistry*, 141(4), 4344–4348.
- Abdulra'uf, L. B., Sirhan, A. Y., et al. (2012). Recent developments and applications of liquid phase microextraction in fruits and vegetables analysis. *Journal of Separation Science*, 35(24), 3540–3553.
- Abubakar, Y., Tijjani, H., Egbuna, C., Adetunji, C. O., Kala, S., Kryeziu, T. L., ... & Patrick-Iwuanyanwu, K. C. (2020). Pesticides, history, and classification. In *Natural remedies for pest, disease and weed control* (pp. 29–42). Academic Press.
- Adetunji, C. O., Oloke, J. K., & Osemwegie, O. O. (2018). Environmental fate and effects of granular pesta formulation from strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* C1501 and *Lasiodiplodia pseudotheobromae* C1136 on soil activity and weeds. *Chemosphere*, 195, 98–107.
- Akhtar, M., Sengupta, W. D., & Chowdhury, A. (2009). Impact of pesticides use in agriculture: Their benefits and hazards. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology*, 2(1), 1–12.
- Aktar, W., Paramasivam, M., Sengupta, D., Purkait, S., Ganguly, M., & Banerjee, S. (2008). Impact assessment of pesticide residues in fish of Ganga river around Kolkata in West Bengal. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 157, 97–104.
- Akter, L., Kobir, M. A., Nasrin, M., Siddiqi, M. N. H., Pervin, M., & Karim, M. R. (2023). Effects of exposure to imidacloprid-contaminated feed on the visceral organs of adult male rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 30(7), 103684.
- Al-Arami, A. M., & Al-Sanabani, A. S. (2021). Histopathological effects of pesticide imidacloprid insecticide on the liver in male rabbits. *Ibn AL-Haitham Journal for Pure and Applied Sciences*, 34(4), 1–9.
- Amjad, A. (2018). A review of imidacloprid toxicity in coccinellids. *Arthropods*, 7(1), 1.
- Asogwa, E. U. (2008). Crop protection practices for cashew and cocoa production in Nigeria. Paper presented at the National Training Workshop for Farmers Development Union (FADU) Officials on Cocoa and Cashew Production in Nigeria. Ibadan.
- Badgujar, P. C., Jain, S. K., Singh, A., Punia, J. S., Gupta, R. P., & Chandratre, G. A. (2013). Immunotoxic effects of imidacloprid following 28 days of oral exposure in BALB/c mice. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 35, 408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2013.01.012>
- Bagri, P., Kumar, V., & Sikka, A. K. (2016). Assessment of imidacloprid-induced mutagenic effects in somatic cells of Swiss albino male mice. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 39, 412–417. <https://doi.org/10.3109/01480545.2015.1137301>
- Baroso, J. (2013). Commission implementing regulation (EU) no 485/2013 of 24 May 2013. *Official Journal of European Union*, 139, 12–26.
- Becker, H., Vogel, W., & Terrier, C. (1988). Embryotoxicity study (including teratogenicity) with NTN 33893 technical in the rat. Unpublished Report No. R 4582. Submitted to WHO by Bayer AG, Mannheim, Germany.
- Becker, H., Vogel, W., & Terrier, C. (1988). Embryotoxicity study (including teratogenicity) with NTN 33893 technical in the rabbit. Unpublished Report No. R 4583. Submitted to WHO by Bayer AG, Mannheim, Germany.
- Bernardes, M. F. F., Pazin, M., Pereira, L. C., & Dorta, D. J. (2015). Impact of pesticides on environmental and human health. In *Toxicology Studies—Cells, Drugs and Environment* (pp. 195–233). IntechOpen.
- Buchel, K. H. (1983). *Chemistry of pesticides*. John Wiley & Sons.
- California Environmental Protection Agency. (2006). *Imidacloprid risk characterization document: Dietary and drinking water exposure*. Department of Pesticide Regulation.
- Carvalho, F. P. (2017). Pesticides, environment, and food safety. *Food Energy Security*, 6, 48–60.
- Chao, S.-L., & Casida, J. E. (1997). Interaction of imidacloprid metabolites and analogs with nicotinic acetylcholine receptor of mouse brain in relation to toxicity. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 58, 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.1006/pest.1997.2284>

- Costa-Valle, M. T., Cestonaro, L. V., Antunes, B. P., Sates, C., ... & Arbo, M. D. (2022). Imidacloprid-based commercial pesticide causes behavioral, biochemical, and hematological impairments in Wistar rats. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, *94*, 103924.
- Di Muccio, A., Fidente, P., Barbini, D. A., Dommarco, R., Seccia, S., & Morrica, P. (2006). Application of solid-phase extraction and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry to the determination of neonicotinoid pesticide residues in fruit and vegetables. *Journal of Chromatography A*, *1108*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2005.12.111>
- Duzguner, V., & Erdogan, S. (2010). Acute oxidant and inflammatory effects of imidacloprid on the mammalian central nervous system and liver in rats. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, *97*, 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2009.11.008>
- Duzguner, V., & Erdogan, S. (2012). Chronic exposure to imidacloprid induces inflammation and oxidative stress in the liver and central nervous system of rats. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, *104*, 58–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2012.06.011>
- Elgharib, I. M., Abdelhamid, F. M., Elshopakey, G., Fawzy, M., & Risha, E. F. (2023). The ameliorative effect of vitamin C against hematological, biochemical, oxidative and immunosuppressive effect of cadmium chloride in rats. *Egyptian Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, *54*(3), 379–394.
- Fenik, J., Tankiewicz, M., & Biziuk, M. (2011). Properties and determination of pesticides in fruits and vegetables. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, *30*, 814–826.
- Fishel, F. M., & Ferrell, J. A. (2013). *Managing pesticide drift* (PI232). University of Florida.
- Furlan, L., & Toffanin, F. (1998). Effectiveness of new insecticides used as seed dressing (imidacloprid and fipronil) against wireworms in controlled environment. *Atti delle Giornate Fitopatologiche (Italy)*.
- Gawade, L., Dadarkar, S. S., Husain, R., & Gatne, M. (2013). A detailed study of developmental immunotoxicity of imidacloprid in Wistar rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *51*, 61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2012.09.009>
- Hayes, T. B., Hansen, M., Kapuscinski, A. R., Locke, K. A., & Barnosky, A. (2017). From silent spring to silent night: Agrochemicals and the Anthropocene. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene*, *5*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.246>
- Hernández, A. F., Gil, F., Lacasaña, M., Rodríguez-Barranco, M., Tsatsakis, A. M., Requena, M., & Alarcón, R. P. (2013). Pesticide exposure and genetic variation in xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes interact to induce biochemical liver damage. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *61*, 144–151.
- Iturburu, F. G., Bertrand, L., Mendieta, J. R., Ame, M. V., & Menone, M. L. (2018a). An integrated biomarker response study explains more than the sum of the parts: Oxidative stress in the fish *Australoheros facetus* exposed to imidacloprid. *Ecological Indicators*, *93*, 351–357.
- Iturburu, F. G., Simoniello, M. F., Medici, S., Panzeri, A. M., & Menone, M. L. (2018b). Imidacloprid causes DNA damage in fish: Clastogenesis as a mechanism of genotoxicity. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, *100*, 760–764.
- Iturburu, F. G., Zömisich, M., Panzeri, A. M., Crupkin, A. C., Contardo Jara, V., & Pflugmacher, S., et al. (2017). Uptake, distribution in different tissues, and genotoxicity of imidacloprid in the freshwater fish *Australoheros facetus*. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, *36*, 699–708.
- Jafarbeigi, F., Samih, M. A., Zarabi, M., et al. (2014). Sublethal effects of some botanical and chemical insecticides on the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). *Arthropods*, *3*(3), 127–137.
- Kobir, A., Siddiqi, N. H., Nasrin, M., Akter, L., Pervin, M., Haque, Z., & Karim, M. R. (2023). Effects of imidacloprid-contaminated feed exposure on the spleen, lymph node, and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissues of adult male rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, *37*(4), 813–819.
- Kola, R. I., & Lawal, S. L. (1999). Degradation of aquatic environment by agro-chemicals in the Middle Belt of Nigeria. In A. Osuntokun (Ed.), *Environmental problems of Nigeria* (pp. 78–88). Davidson Press.
- Leong, W. H., Teh, S. Y., Hossain, M. M., Nadarajaw, T., Zabidi-Hussin, Z., Chin, S. Y., & Lim, S. H. E. (2020). Application, monitoring and adverse effects in pesticide use: The importance of reinforcement of Good Agricultural Practices (GAPs). *Journal of Environmental Management*, *260*, 109987.
- Lin, N., & Garry, V. (2000). In vitro studies of cellular and molecular developmental toxicity of adjuvants, herbicides, and fungicides commonly used in Red River Valley, Minnesota. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A: Current Issues*, *60*, 423–439.
- Liu, M. Y., & Casida, J. E. (1993). High-affinity binding of [3H]-imidacloprid in the insect acetylcholine receptor. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, *46*, 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1006/pest.1993.1034>

- Lonare, M., Kumar, M., Raut, S., Badgujar, P., Doltade, S., & Telang, A. (2014). Evaluation of imidacloprid-induced neurotoxicity in male rats: A protective effect of curcumin. *Neurochemistry International*, 78, 122–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuint.2014.09.004>
- Matsuda, K., Buckingham, S. D., Kleier, D., Rauh, J. J., Grauso, M., & Sattelle, D. B. (2001). Neonicotinoids: Insecticides acting on insect nicotinic acetylcholine receptors. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 22, 573–580. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-6147\(00\)01820-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-6147(00)01820-4)
- Meijden, G. V. (1998). *Pesticide application techniques in West Africa*. FAO.
- Mikolić, A., & Karačonji, I. B. (2018). Imidacloprid as reproductive toxicant and endocrine disruptor: Investigations in laboratory animals. *Arhiv za Higijenu Rada i Toksikologiju*, 69(2), 103–108.
- Naiel, M. A., Shehata, A. M., Negm, S. S., Abd El-Hack, M. E., Amer, M. S., Khafaga, A. F., & Allam, A. A. (2020). The new aspects of using some safe feed additives on alleviated imidacloprid toxicity in farmed fish: A review. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 12(4), 2250–2267.
- Perez-Iglesias, J. M., De Arcaute, C. R., Nikoloff, N., Dury, L., Soloneski, S., & Natale, G. S., et al. (2014). The genotoxic effects of the imidacloprid-based insecticide formulation Glacoxan Imida on Montevideo tree frog *Hypsiboas pulchellus* tadpoles (Anura, Hylidae). *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 104, 120–126.
- Peritore, A. F., Franco, G. A., Molinari, F., Arangia, A., Interdonato, L., Marino, Y., & Crupi, R. (2023). Effect of pesticide vinclozolin toxicity exposure on cardiac oxidative stress and myocardial damage. *Toxics*, 11(6), 473.
- Pesticides Residue Committee. (2004). *Report 2004*. http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/agphome/documents/Pests_Pesticides/JMPR/Reports_1991-2006/report2004jmpr.pdf
- Raza, W., Tripathi, N., Mahato, D., & Mahto, D. (n.d.). Effects of imidacloprid on biochemical and hematological parameters in *Cirrhinus mrigala*: An updated review.
- Rola, A., & Pingali, P. (1993). *Pesticides, rice productivity, and farmers' health: An economic assessment* (pp. 25–30). IRRI, International Rice Research Institute.
- Rortais, A., Arnold, G., Dorne, J. L., More, S. J., Sperandio, G., & Streissl, F., et al. (2017). Risk assessment of pesticides and other stressors in bees: Principles, data gaps and perspectives from the European Food Safety Authority. *Science of the Total Environment*, 587, 524–537.
- Ross, G. (2005). Risks and benefits of DDT. *Lancet*, 366(9499), 1771–1772.
- Saadi, L., Mahboubi, Y., & Matallah, R. (2014). Inflammatory effects of imidacloprid on thyroid activity in rats. In *International Conference on Civil, Biological and Environmental Engineering (CBEE-2014)*, Istanbul, Turkey. <http://iicbe.org/upload/9427C514572.pdf>
- Saqer, B. T., Al-Aubadi, I. M., & Ali, A. J. (2019). Study on the effect of imidacloprid in blood, liver and kidney on adult male albino mice. *Biochemical & Cellular Archives*, 19(2).
- Smit, C., Posthuma-Doodeman, C., Van Vlaardingen, P. D., & De Jong, F. (2015). Ecotoxicity of imidacloprid to aquatic organisms: Derivation of water quality standards for peak and long-term exposure. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 21, 1608–1630.
- Smith, R. L., & Smith, T. M. (1998). *Elements of ecology* (4th ed., pp. 235–240, 9, 10, 144). Addison Wesley Longman Inc.
- Stoughton, S. J., Liber, K., Culp, J., & Cessna, A. (2008). Acute and chronic toxicity of imidacloprid to the aquatic invertebrates *Chironomus tentans* and *Hyaella azteca* under constant- and pulse-exposure conditions. *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 54, 662–673.
- Strassemeyer, J., Daehmlow, D., Dominic, A., Lorenz, S., & Golla, B. (2017). SYNOPSIS-WEB, an online tool for environmental risk assessment to evaluate pesticide strategies on field level. *Crop Protection*, 97, 28–44.
- Struik, P. C., & Bonciarelli, F. (1997). Resource use at the cropping system level. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 7, 133–143.
- Tano, Z. J. (2011). Identity, physical and chemical properties of pesticides. In *Pesticides in the modern world: Trends in pesticides analysis* (pp. 1–18). InTechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/15711>
- Tisler, T., Jemec, A., Mozetic, B., & Trebse, P. (2009). Hazard identification of imidacloprid to aquatic environment. *Chemosphere*, 76, 907–914.
- Tomizawa, M. (2013). Chemical biology of the nicotinic insecticide receptor. In *Advances in Insect Physiology* (Vol. 44, pp. 145–176). Elsevier.
- Tomizawa, M., & Casida, J. E. (2005). Neonicotinoid insecticide toxicology: Mechanisms of selective action. *Annual Review of Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 45, 247–268.
- Tomlin, C. D. S. (Ed.). (1997). *The pesticide manual* (11th ed., pp. 706–708). British Crop Protection Council.

- Tudi, M., Ruan, H. D., Wang, L., Lyu, J., Sadler, R., Connell, D., & Phung, D. T. (2021). Agriculture development, pesticide application and its impact on the environment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(3), 1112.
- United States Environmental Protection Agency. (2003). *Imidacloprid, pesticide tolerances*. US EPA.
- Van Dijk, T. C., Van Staalduinen, M. A., & Van Der Sluijs, J. P. (2013). Macro-invertebrate decline in surface water polluted with imidacloprid. *PLoS ONE*, 8(5), e62374.
- Youdeowei, A. (1989). *Provisional report on pesticide management in Anglophone West Africa*. Prepared for FAO Rome.
- Zadoks, J. C., & Waibel, H. (2000). From pesticides to genetically modified plants: History, economics and politics. *Netherlands Journal of Agricultural Science*, 48, 125–149.
- Zhang, A., Kaiser, H., Maienfisch, P., & Casida, J. E. (2000). Insect nicotinic acetylcholine receptor: Conserved neonicotinoid specificity of [3H]-imidacloprid binding site. *Journal of Neurochemistry*, 75, 1294–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-4159.2000.751294.x>
- Zhang, W. J. (2018). Global pesticide use: Profile, trend, cost/benefit and more. *Proceedings of the International Academy of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 8(1), 1–27.
- Zhang, W. J., Jiang, F. B., & Ou, J. F. (2011). Global pesticide consumption and pollution: With China as a focus. *Proceedings of the International Academy of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 1(2), 125–144.